

ADVANCED HOSPITAL MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

AN
INTERNSHIP REPORT
ON
ADVANCED HOSPITAL MANAGEMENT
SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT
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CHAPTER-1

INTRODUCTION

Introduction:

Human Body is an extremely intricate and modern structure and involves a huge number of capacities. All these muddled capacities have been comprehended by man him, part-by-part their exploration and tests. As science and innovation advanced, pharmaceutical turned into a necessary part of the exploration. Continuously, restorative science turned into an altogether new branch of science. Starting today, the Health Sector involves Medical establishments i.e. Healing facilities, HOSPITALs and so forth innovative work foundations and medicinal universities. In this way the Health division goes for giving the best therapeutic offices to the basic man.

Medical Institutions in Nepal

As yet being a creating country Nepal has seen a huge development of the Health part in the field of examination and in addition in the field of advancement of various expansive and little scale Hospital organizations as yet ailing in between structure offices. Legislature of Nepal has still gone for giving restorative offices by building up healing facility. The essential working of different healing facilities in Nepal is still on paper when contrasted with doctor's facilities in European nations where PCs have been placed into help the doctor's facility personals their work. The idea of robotization of the organization and administration of doctor's facility is currently being actualized in Nepal likewise, with substantial doctor's facilities like APPOLO and AIIMS in Kathmandu, ESCORTS in Kathmandu, having computerized their current framework.

ADVANCED HOSPITAL MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

Our task depends on the above idea i.e. mechanization of Administration and Management of Hospital. The undertaking has been created keeping in-perspective the accompanying angles: -

- (i) Working environment of the Hospital.
- (ii) The point of view and disposition of Nepal individuals.
- (iii) The proficiency rate of Nepal.
- (iv) The Existing framework, being utilized as a part of the lion's share of Hospitals.
- (v) The accessibility of Infra-auxiliary offices likes fund, gifted personals, and workplace.

DEFINITION OF PROBLEM:

Since HOSPITAL is connected with the lives of normal individuals and their everyday schedules so I chose to take a shot at this anticipate.

The manual treatment of the record is tedious and very inclined to mistake. The reason for this anticipate is to mechanize or make on the web, the procedure of everyday exercises like Room exercises, Admission of New Patient, Discharge of Patient, Assign a Doctor, lastly figure the bill and so on.

I have attempted my best to make the confounded procedure Hospital Management System as basic as could be allowed utilizing Structured and Modular strategy and

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Menu situated interface. I have attempted to plan the product in a manner that client might not have any trouble in utilizing this bundle and further extension is conceivable without much exertion. Despite the fact that I can't guarantee that this work to be altogether thorough, the primary motivation behind my activity is play out every Hospital's action in electronic path instead of physically which is tedious.

I am certain that this product bundle can be promptly utilized by non-programming individual staying away from human took care of possibility of mistake.

DRAWBACKS OF CURRENT MANUAL- SYSTEM

1. The current manual framework has a considerable measure of printed material and it doesn't manage old and new auto buy and deal.
2. To keep up the records of offer and administration physically, is a Time-expending work.
3. With the expansion in database, it will end up being a monstrous employment to keep up the database.
4. Requires expansive amounts of file organizers, which are gigantic and require a considerable amount of space in the workplace, which can be utilized for putting away records of past subtle elements.
5. The recovery of records of already enrolled patients will be a repetitive occupation.

6. Lack of security for the records, anybody disarrange the records of your framework.

7. If somebody need to check the points of interest of the accessible specialists the past framework does not give any fundamental subtle element of this write.

ESTABLISH THE NEED OF NEW SYSTEM

1. Problem of Reliability: Current framework is not dependable. It appears to change in quality from one month to the, following. Some of the time it gives great yield, yet some times the yield is most exceedingly bad.

2. Problem of Accuracy: There are an excessive number of missteps in reports.

3. Problem of auspiciousness: In the present framework the reports and yield delivered is for the most part late and in the majority of the cases it is pointless in light of the fact that it is not on time.

4. Problem of Validity: The yield and reports for the most part contains deluding data. The client's data is now and again not substantial.

5. Problem of Economy: The present framework is expensive. We need to spend bunches of cash to keep the framework up and going, yet at the same time not get the sought results.

6. **Problem of Capacity:** The present framework is experiencing issue of limit too. The staff for association is less and the workload is excessively. Few people groups can't deal with all the work.

PROPOSED SYSTEM

1. Doctor Details: The new proposed system admin can add doctors details and maintains all the doctor details.

2. Bill details: The new proposed system calculates bill of patient and maintain in database of each patient bill.

3. Registers: There is no need of keeping and maintaining patients manually. It remembers each and every record and we can get any report related to patient and at any time.

4. Speed: The new proposed system is very fast with 100% accuracy and saves time.

5. Manpower: The new proposed system needs less manpower. Less people can do the large work.

6. Efficiency: The new proposed systems complete the work of many salesperson in less time.

7. Past details: The new proposed system contains the details of every past doctor and patients for future assistance.

8. Reduces redundancy: The most important benefit of this system is that it reduces the redundancy of data within the data.

9. Work load: Reduces the work load of the data store by helping in easy updates of the products and providing them with the necessary details together with financial transactions management.

10. Easy statements: Month-end and day-end statement easily taken out without getting headaches on browsing through the day end statements.

NEED:

I have planned the given proposed framework in the PHP to robotize the procedure of everyday exercises of Hospital like Room exercises, Admission of New Patient, Discharge of Patient, Assign a Doctor, lastly register the bill and so forth., online offices to the numerous clients and so on.

The complete arrangement of standards and methods identified with Hospital's everyday exercises and creating report is called "ONLINE CLINIC SYSTEM". My venture gives a brief thought with respect to computerized Hospital exercises.

The accompanying strides that give the itemized data of the need of proposed framework are:

Execution: During recent decades, the doctor's facility administration framework should keep up manual treatment of all the clinic every day exercises. The manual treatment of the record is tedious and profoundly inclined to mistake. To enhance the execution of the doctor's facility administration framework, the mechanized healing facility administration framework is to be embraced. The modernized doctor's facility undertaking is completely mechanized and easy to use even that any of the doctor's facility's individuals can see the patient's report and the specialist's report.

Productivity: The fundamental need of the undertaking is proficiency. The task ought to be effective so that at whatever point another patient is conceded, and naturally a bed is doled out furthermore a specialist is doled out to the patient as indicated by the patient's infection. What's more, if any patient is getting released, the bed doled out to him/her ought to naturally free in the PC.

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Control: The complete control of the task is under the hands of approved individual who has the secret word to get to this anticipate and illicit access shouldn't manage. All the control is under the manager and alternate individuals have the rights to quite recently see the records not to change any exchange or passage.

Security: Security is the principle criteria for the proposed framework. Since unlawful access may degenerate the database and it will influence the doctor's facility as well as it likewise influences the patient's life. So security must be given in this anticipate.

CHAPTER-2
OBJECTIVE & SCOPE OF THE
PROJECT

Objective

The aim of this project i.e. ONLINE CLINIC SYSTEM is all about train system from anywhere, anytime. The extra feature involved is our ticket details which keeps the patient in touch. Our application is that it is secured in a way that only registered doctor can enter this application which have valid password and id.

Main Objectives are :-

- The ONLINE CLINIC SYSTEM is meant to keep the security of the admin and between the Patient.
- After login admin can search Patient bill status.
- Admin can maintain the details of doctor and patient.
- The main concern of this project is to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of the whole system.

Other Objectives

- User friendly interface.
- All forms are html templates driven
- Integration among all functional areas.
- The availability of the information is easy.
- Routine tasks are easily performed.
- It automates the redundant tasks.
- It will save time and money.
- In summary we can say that main objective of the project is to make the work easy and smooth.
- It will provide the better customer service and enhance the profit of the organization.

CHAPTER-3
TOOLS/ENVIRONMENT
USED

3.1 FRONT END

ABOUT PHP:-

PHP: Hypertext Preprocessor is a broadly utilized, universally useful scripting dialect that was initially intended for web advancement to deliver dynamic site pages. For this reason, PHP code is implanted into the HTML source report and deciphered by a web server with a PHP processor module, which creates the page archive. As a broadly useful programming dialect, PHP code is prepared by a translator application in summon line mode performing wanted working framework operations and creating program yield on its standard yield channel. It might likewise work as a graphical application. PHP is accessible as a processor for most cutting edge web servers and as a standalone mediator on most working frameworks and figuring stages.

PHP was initially made by Rasmus Lerdorf in 1995 and has been in nonstop advancement from that point onward. The principle usage of PHP is currently created by the PHP Group and serves as the accepted standard for PHP as there is no formal determination. PHP is free programming discharged under the PHP License.

PHP is a broadly useful scripting dialect that is particularly suited to server-side web advancement where PHP for the most part keeps running on a web server. Any PHP code in an asked for document is executed by the PHP runtime, more often than not to make dynamic site page content. It can likewise be utilized for order line scripting and customer side GUI applications. PHP can be sent on most web servers, numerous working frameworks and stages, and can be utilized with numerous social database administration frameworks. It is accessible gratis, and the PHP Group gives the complete source code to clients to manufacture, alter and reach out for their own utilization.

PHP principally goes about as a channel, taking contribution from a document or stream containing content and/or PHP directions and yields another flood of information; most ordinarily the yield will be HTML. Since PHP 4, the PHP parser arranges contribution to deliver byte code for preparing by the Zend Engine, giving enhanced execution over its translator forerunner.

Initially intended to make dynamic pages, PHP now concentrates essentially on server-side scripting, and it is like other server-side scripting dialects that give dynamic substance from a web server to a customer.

The LAMP design has ended up famous in the web business as a method for conveying web applications. PHP is normally utilized as the P as a part of this pack nearby Linux, Apache and My SQL.. WAMP bundles (Windows/Apache/MySQL/PHP) and MAMP bundles (Macintosh/Apache/MySQL/PHP) are additionally accessible.

As of April 2007, more than 20 million Internet spaces had web administrations facilitated on servers with PHP introduced and mod_php was recorded as the most well known Apache HTTP Server module.

Noteworthy site are composed in PHP including the client confronting part of Facebook.

Points of interest TO PHP:-

- Open Source, promptly accessible (you can utilize it today) and double authorized - on the off chance that you are doing non-benefit work or not permitting, there is no expense.
- Very Easy to comprehend Syntax, some truly cool components (clusters are something else!)

- Interfaces effectively with Apache/MySQL
- Server side .
- Lots of good source code out there to utilize and/or gain from, too the same number of valuable libraries for working with PDFs, design, and so on.
- Lots of good books and on-line help (php.net is incredible)
- Platform rationalist, can keep running on Windows Linux or Mac servers. Too extremely adaptable.
- Lots of facilitating administrations have it prepared to utilize, no uncommon arrangement (aside from in the event that you have uncommon security needs)
- Pretty simple to get to other online devices through PHP (i.e. google maps, and so on

HOW PHP WORKS.

2) Profile of issue:-

Issues with customary framework

1. Absence of prompt recoveries: - The data is extremely hard to recover also, to discover specific data like-E.g. - To get some answers concerning the patient's history, the client needs to experience different registers. This outcomes in hindrance what's more, wastage of time.

2. Absence of prompt data stockpiling: - The data produced by different exchanges requires some investment and endeavors to be put away at ideal spot.
3. Absence of brief overhauling: - Various changes to data like patient points of interest or vaccination subtle elements of youngster are hard to make as printed material is included.
4. Blunder inclined manual count: - Manual estimations are mistake inclined and take a great deal of time this may bring about off base data. For instance count of patient's bill in view of different medications.
5. Planning of exact and incite reports: - This turns into a troublesome errand as data is hard to gather from different registers.

Introduction to HTML

The hypertext markup lingo (HTML) is a fundamental markup vernacular. Used to make a hypertext reports that are minimal beginning with one phase then onto the following HTML records are SGML (Standard summed up engraving up lingo) files with tasteless semantics that are fitting for addressing information from a broad assortment of usages. This point of interest describes HTML variation

3.2. HTML 3.2 arrangements to find endorsed work on beginning mid '96 and in that limit an exchange for HTML2.0 (RFC 1866).

A course of action of rules introduced in a chronicle is rung mark vernacular. These headings depict what the record content means and how it should look like in a dPaper Less Hospitalallay. Hyper Text Mark Up lingo (HTML) is the tongue used to encode World Wide Web records.

WHY TO USE HTML?

Site is a gathering of pages, distributions, and records that dwell on web server. While these pages productions and an archive as a designed in a solitary organization, you ought to utilize HTML for landing page and all essential pages in the site. This will empower the a large number of web clients can without much of a stretch get to and to exploit your site.

HTML is viewed as first to format any new material you plan to distribute on the web. HTML records are stage free, implying that they don't affirm to any standard. In the event that they are made legitimately you can move landing page to any server stage or you can get to them with any protest www program.

STRUCTURE OF HTML

HTML components play out a characterized undertaking. HTML utilizes two sorts of components . Unfilled Tags

. Holder Tags

These labels contrast in view of what they speak to. Vacant labels speak to arranging tightens, for example, line breaks and level principles. Compartment labels characterize an area of content, arrangements and spot the greater part of the chose content. A holder tag has both a starting and a consummation.

HTML LAYOUT:

A HTML report comprises of content, which includes the substance of the archive and labels, which, characterizes the structure, and appearance of the record. The structure of a HTML record is basic, comprises of external.

<HTML>tag enclosing the document header and body

<HTML>

<HEAD>

<TITLE>the title of HTML document</TITLE>

</HEAD>

<BODY>

This is where the actual HTML documents

Text lies, which is dPaper Less Hospitallayed in the browser

</BODY>

</HTML>

Every record has a head and body delimited by the <HEAD> and <BODY> tag. The head is the place you give your HTML record a title and where you demonstrate different parameters the program may utilize when dPaper Less Hospitallaying the archive. This incorporates the content for dPaper Less Hospitallaying the content. Tag additionally references exceptional and demonstrates the problem areas that connection your archive to different reports.

HTML FORMS:

Making a structure as a rule includes two free strides: Creating the design for the structure itself and afterward composing a script program on the server side to handle the arrangement you get once more from a structure.

To make a structure, You utilize the <FORM> tag. Inside the opening and shutting FORM labels are each of the individual

structure components in addition to whatever other HTML substance to make a design for that structure.

The opening tag of the FORM component for the most part incorporates the traits: METHOD and ACTION. The METHOD qualities can be either GET or POST which decides how your structure information is sent to the script to process it.

The ACTION credit is a pointer to the script that procedures the structure on the server side. The ACTION can be incorporated by a relative way or by a full URL to a script on your server or elsewhere. For instance, the accompanying <FORM> tag would call a script called structure name in cgi-container registry on server www.myserver.com

```
<FORM Method= post action=http://www.myserver.com/cgi-container/structure name.pl>
```

```
</FORM>
```

Technique ATTRIBUTE:

The other required trait for the <form> label sets the techniques by which the program structure's information to the server for

handling. There are two ways: the POST technique and GET strategy. With POST technique, the program sends the information in two stages: the program first contacts the structure handling server indicated in the activity properties, and once contact is made, sends the information.

The GET technique in the other hand, contacts the structure handling server and sends the structure information in a solitary exchange step: the program annexes the information to the structure's activity URL, isolated by the question mark (?) character.

Prologue to JavaScript

JavaScript:

JavaScript is another scripting dialect for WebPages. Scripts composed with java script can be inserted into your HTML pages. With java script you have numerous conceivable outcomes for upgrading your HTML page with intriguing components. For instance you can react to client started occasions effectively. Some impacts that are presently conceivable with java script were some time back just conceivable with CGI. So you can make truly complex pages with the aides of java script on the Internet.

Contrast amongst java and Java Script

In spite of the fact that the names are practically the same Java is not the same as Java Script. These are two unique methods for Internet programming. Java Paper Less Hospitalprogramming dialect. JavaScript is a scripting dialect as the name suggests. The distinction is that we can make genuine projects with java. However, java script is not genuine programming. Java Script is intended to be straightforward and simple to utilize. JavaScript creators ought not need to think a lot about programming. We could say that Java Script is preferably an augmentation to HTML than a different coding. Obviously this is not the official definition but rather it makes it simpler to comprehend the distinction amongst java and java script.

By what method can Java Script scripts run?

The principal program to bolster java script was the Netscape Navigator 2.0 obviously the higher forms do have java script also. You may realize that java does not keep running on all Netscape Navigators 2.0 (or higher renditions) adaptations. Yet, this is not valid for java script - despite the fact that there are a few issues with the diverse forms.

The Mac form for instance appears to have numerous bugs. Sooner rather than later there will be some different programs, which bolster java script. The Microsoft Internet adventurer 3.0 is going to bolster java script. JavaScript empowered programs are going to spread soon - it merits taking in this new strategy now. You may understand that is truly simple to compose Java Script scripts. We need to know is some fundamental systems and some work-around for issues you may experience. Obviously we require a fundamental. Understanding HTML before understanding this instructional exercise you can discover numerous better than average online assets about HTML. Best you make an online pursuit about "html" at yippee on the off chance that you need to get educated about HTML. Presently I need to demonstrate some little scripts so you can figure out how they are executed into HTML-archives and to show which potential outcomes you have with the new scripting dialect. The accompanying is a little script, which will just print a content into a HTML record.

```
<html>
```

```
<head>
```

```
My first JavaScript
```

```
</head>
```

```
<body><br>
```

This is an ordinary HTML archive

```
<br>
```

```
<script language="JavaScript">
```

```
Document.write ("this is a java script")
```

```
</script><b r>
```

Backing HTML once more

```
</body>
```

```
</html>
```

On the off chance that you are utilizing a java script empowered program right now then you will have the likelihood to see this script working. In the event that your program doesn't bolster Java Script then this yield may be some sort of peculiar...

This is an ordinary HTML record

This is java script!

Back in HTML once more.

Capacities

Capacities are wagered proclaimed between the <Head> tag of HTML page. Capacities are called by client started occasions. Appears to be sensible to keep the capacities between the

<Head> labels. They are stacked first before a client can do anything that may call a capacity. Scripts can be put between inside remark fields to guarantee that more established program don't dPaper Less Hospitallay the script itself.

```
<html>
<head>
<script language="JavaScript">
function pushbutton (){
alert ("Hello!");
}
</script>
</head>
<body>
<form>
<input type="button" name="Button1" value="push me"
onclick="pushbutton ()">
</form>
</body>
</html>
```

On the off chance that we need to test this one promptly and you are utilizing a Java Script empowered program then please simply ahead and push the catch.

This script will make a catch and when you squeeze it a window will appear saying "hi!". Indeed we have a great deal of conceivable outcomes just by adding capacities to our scripts.

The normal programs transmit the structure data by either technique: here's the finished tag including the GET transmission strategy trait for the past structure

Case

```
<Form strategy =GET action=http://www.mycompany.com/cgi-  
canister/upfdate.pl>
```

...

```
</form>
```

Information components.

Utilize the <input> tag to characterize any of various normal structure components including content fields different decision records click capable pictures and accommodation catches. There are numerous attributers for this tag just that sorts and name properties are required for every component, every kind of info component utilizes just a subset of the took after qualities. Extra <input> traits might be required based whereupon kind of the structure component you determine.

Submit catch:

The submit catch (`<input type=submit>`) does what its name suggests, settings in movement the structure's accommodation to the server from the program. We numerous have more than submit catches will be added to the parameter list the program sends along to the server.

Case

```
< Input sort ="submit">
```

```
<Input type="submit" value="submit" name="name">
```

Reset catch:

The reset catch if firm `<input>` catch is about simple; it gives the client a chance to reset eradicate or set to some default esteem all components in the structure. Of course the program dPaper Less Hospitallays a reset catch worth the mark "reset". We can change that by indicating a worth quality with visit own catch name.

Prologue TO JDBC

JDBC (Java Database network) is a front-end device for interfacing with a server to ODBC in that admiration, however JDBC can associate just java customer and it utilizes ODBC for the availability. JDBC is basically a low-level API since any information control, stockpiling and recovery must be finished by the system itself. Some apparatuses, which give a more elevated amount reflection, are normal in no time.

The following question that should be addressed is the reason we require JDBC, once we have ODBC close by. We can utilize the same ODBC to associate the whole database and ODBC is a demonstrated innovation.

Issue for doing this is ODBC gives a "c" dialect API, which utilizes pointers widely. Since java does not have any pointers and is article situated sun Microsystems, innovator of java created to suit its needs.

Necessities to utilize JDBC:

To utilize JDBC you require an essential information of databases and SQL. A part from this you require the jdk1.1 (Java Development Kit1.1 accessible javasoft's site) or an adaptation of Java since jdk1.1 or more come packaged with JDBC programming.

After that you need a back-end database motor for which a JDBC driver is accessible. At the point when JDBC drivers are not accessible JDBC-ODBC span drivers are utilized to get to the database through ODBC. Back-end is not required when JDBC driver is fit for putting away and recovering the information itself, or if JDBC-ODBC Bridge and the ODBC driver can be utilized to store and recover the data.

Prologue To MySql

Present day social database administration frameworks can play out an extensive variety of undertakings. It has the accompanying points of interest-

- Define a database
- Query the database
- Add, alter and erase information.
- Modify the structure of the database
- Secure information from free.
- Communicate inside systems
- Export and import information

MySql is one such RDBMS. It gives an arrangement of useful projects that we utilize an instrument to assemble structure and performs errands, in mysql information is put away and showed in tables. A table is an information structure that holds information in a social database. A table involves lines and sections. Table can likewise indicate relationship between substances. The formal name of table is connection, consequently the name Relational Database Management System.

Access of information in mysql

SQL is an organized inquiry dialect that we use to speak with mysql. It comprises of an arrangement of English words like Select, Create and so on. The standard arrangement of SQL charge fall into the accompanying classification

- Queries utilizing select proviso
- Data definition dialect (DDL) charges which are for making and changing the structure of database.

Notable Features of MySql

- Open Source
- Efficient multi-client backing and consistency
- Powerful security highlight
- Fault resistance
- Ease of organization
- Application advancement instruments
- Networking
- SQL similarity

About SQL

SQL is an organized inquiry dialect that we use to speak with prophet. It comprises of an arrangement of English words like Select, Create and so forth. The standard arrangement of SQL order fall into the accompanying classification.

3.3 Tools / Platform, Hardware and Software Requirement specifications

HARDWARE SPECIFICATION

VIRTUAL MEMEORY

PROCESSOR : 32 BIT, Pentium – IV

RAM : 1 GB

HARD DISK : 40 GB

MONITOR : SVGA Monitor (800 * 600RESOLUTIONS)

CLOCK SPEED : 266 MHz

SOFTWARE SPECIFICATION

OPERATING SYSTEM : Windows 2000/XP.

FRONT END : Php

BACK END : My Sql

CHAPTER-4

ANALYSIS DOCUMENT

SYSTEM ANALYSIS

PRELIMINARY INVESTIGATION

Things are relied upon to get considerably more basic since the organization's developing quantities of customers and related prerequisites have been anticipated to request an enormous number of workers in the coming future from the past and the today's date. Such occasions and projections have constrained a solid requirement for adjustment in the present method for taking care of exercises. It is ideal to execute the most recent of it as opposed to experience the torment of upgrading the framework again and again. Additionally the arrangement would be created by in-house designers. Their time must be made do with their other customer subordinate calendars.

FEASIBILITY STUDY

Contingent upon the consequences of the underlying examination, the overview is extended to a more point by point achievability study. Achievability study is a test of framework proposition as indicated by its workability, sway on the association, capacity to address client issues, and compelling utilization of assets. The target of the attainability study is not to take care of the issue but rather to obtain a feeling of its extension. Amid the study, the issue definition is solidified and parts of the issue to be incorporated into the framework are resolved.

Therefore, expenses and advantages are depicted with more prominent exactness at this stage. It comprises of the accompanying: Articulation of the issue: A painstakingly worded proclamation of the issue that prompted investigation.

TECHNICAL FEASIBILITY

This includes money related contemplations to suit specialized upgrades. In the event that the monetary allowance is a genuine imperative, then the task is judged not practical.

ECONOMICAL FEASIBILITY

With the assistance of managing an account application it will prompt abatement in expense of opening and keeping up workplaces which will be more than the expense of creating and keeping up the Application.

OPERATIONAL FEASIBILITY

This Application is anything but difficult to work as it is made easy to use. Fundamental thought is client's simple access to all the usefulness of the Application.

4.2 IDENTIFICATION OF NEED

To recognize the prerequisite for programming we use the Principles of Requirement Engineering. Need fabricating gives the appropriate instrument to understanding what the customer needs, separating need, looking over plausibility, orchestrating a sensible game plan, showing the course of action unambiguously, tolerating the determination and managing the essential as they are changed into an operational system. The essential planning system can be delineated in five unmistakable steps: -

- Requirement elicitation.
- Requirement examination and exchange.
- Requirement point of interest.
- System Modeling.
- Requirement endorsement.
- Requirement Management.

Toward the day's end we can say that essential examination is an item errand that defeats any issues between system level need building and programming plot. Essential examination allows the item planning to refine the item partition and develop models of the data, helpful and behavioral zones that will be managed by programming. Essential

examination gives the item organizer a representation of information, limit and direct that can be deciphered into data, compositional, interface and part level arrangement; finally the need subtle element gives the architect and the customer with the best approach to review quality once writing computer programs is built.

The most normally used essential elicitation framework is to lead a meeting or meeting. The at first meeting between an item designer and customer can be contrasted with the unwieldiness of a first date between to young people. Neither one of the persons perceives what to say or ask, Both are worried that what they do say will be bewildered, both are reasoning about where it might lead (Both likely have in a general sense unmistakable longing here) Both need to get the completely consider with, yet meanwhile, both need it to be a win.

Here according to this administer the inspector starts by asking setting free-addresses. That is a course of action of request that will provoke a crucial understanding of the issue, the all inclusive community who require an answer, the nature of game plan that is longed for, and the ampleness of the principle experience itself. The principle course of action of without connection question focuses on the customer, the

general goals, and the points of interest. Case in point, the specialist may ask: -

- Who is behind the sales for this work?
- Who will use the course of action?
- What will be monetary favorable position of a compelling course of action?
- Is there another hotspot for the Solution that you require?

The accompanying course of action of the request enables the item draftsman to get a prevalent Understanding of the issue and the customer to voice his or her perceptions around an answer: -

- How would you portray "awesome" yield that would be delivered by a productive course of action?
- What problem(s) will this course of action location?
- Can you exhibit me (or portray) the earth in which the course of action will be used?
- Will unprecedented execution issues or constraints impact the strategy for the course of action is moved closer?
- Are you the perfect individual to answer these request? Are your answers? Official"?
- Are my request critical to the issue that you have?

- Am I soliciting an intemperate number from request?
- Can whatever other individual give additional information?
- Should I be asking you something else?

As demonstrated by the above thoughts I went to the diverse IT associations and met its staffs, organization, and a couple of persons related with the definitive work, which incited me related with my errand.

Preliminary Investigation

The initial phase in the framework advancement life cycle is the preparatory examination to decide the attainability of the System. The reason for the preparatory examination is to assess venture demands. It is neither an outline study nor does it incorporates the gathering of points of interest top portray the business framework in all admiration. Or maybe, it is gathering of data that helps board of trustees individuals to assess the benefits of the task demand and make an educated judgment about the achievability of the proposed venture.

Here for the "**HOSPITAL MANAGEMENT SYSTEM**", I have dealt with the preparatory examination that fulfilled the accompanying targets:

- Clarify and comprehend the task demand.
- Determine the measure of the undertaking.
- Assess expenses and advantages of option methodologies.

- Determine the specialized and operational plausibility of option methodologies.

Report the discoveries to administration with suggestion sketching out the acknowledgments or dismissal of the proposition.

Considering above criteria I likewise remember that the necessities are obviously reasonable when the illumination of undertaking solicitation is enquired. The information of the IT Companies which are gathered by me amid preparatory examination, are: -

- Reviewing association Documents
- Onsite perception and
- Conducting interviews.

Feasibility Study

Not all that matters believable is plausible, not even in programming, transient as it might appear to untouchables. Plausibility is the determination of regardless of whether a task merits doing. In actuality, programming achievability has seven strong measurements as underneath: -

1. Technical achievability.
2. Operational possibility.
3. Economic possibility.

The procedure followed in making this determination is known as a possibility study. This sort of study decides when a venture can or ought to be taken. When it has been resolved that the undertaking is attainable, and afterward examiner can simply ahead and set up the venture particular, which settles venture prerequisites. For the most part, practicality studies are attempted inside tight time imperatives and ordinarily come full circle in a composed and oral plausibility report. The substance and proposal of such a study will be utilized as a sound premise for choosing whether to continue, put off or drop the venture. In this manner, since the plausibility study may prompt the dedication of huge assets, it gets to be essential that it ought to be led ably and that no basic blunders of judgment are made.

At the end of the day we can say that a plausibility study is led to choose the best framework that meets execution necessity. This contains and distinguishing proof depiction, an assessment of hopeful framework and the determination of most ideally equipped framework for the employment. The framework required an announcement of imperatives; the recognizable proof of particular

framework objective and a portrayal of yields characterize execution.

a) Technical Feasibility

Technical feasibility is concerned with specifying equipment and software that will successfully satisfy the user requirements. My project is fit in technical feasibility because it requires neither too much heavy configuration system for its run nor in its development.

b) Economical Feasibility

Monetary investigation is the most as often as possible utilized method for assessment of the adequacy of a proposed framework. All the more normally known as Cost/Benefit examination, the technique is to decide the advantages and sparing that are normal from a proposed framework and contrast them and expenses. On the off chance that advantages exceed costs, a choice is taken to plan and actualize the framework. Other weight costs, a choice is taken to outline and execute the framework. Something else, further defense or option in the proposed framework will must be made if is to have a possibility of being affirmed. This is an on going exertion that enhances in exactness at every period of the framework life cycle.

c) Operational Feasibility

My task is additionally fit in Operational Feasibility Study. As I have clarified before this about Technical Feasibility and Economical Feasibility, this Software is simple and easy to understand.

I have utilized a simple menu framework furthermore utilized some control catches as a part of the easy route by which one can pick the choices on his yearning. In spite of the fact that this is completely ensured with the security by word (Password and client name),If both are coordinated at exactly that point one can get access of this product. Different Reports, Forms and Queries can be produced on the fingertips for the client. In nutshell we can say that it has taking after operational elements:

1. It is User-Friendly.
2. It is having less printed material.
3. Efficient tractability.
4. Query can be created.

Project Planning

The arranging, outline, and establishment of a framework termed a task and is coordinated by a venture pioneer who utilizes the accessible assets to create another or better framework for the associations.

In this way, extend anticipating any organization has the accompanying four principle steps:

1. Sorting out the assets accessible for the task.

2. Booking the occasions of the task.
3. Assessing the advancement.
4. Setting up benchmarks for the undertaking.

A compelling administrator is crucial for fruitful venture arranging.

The strategies of venture arranging are not a substitute for good administration, but rather only an instrument to be utilized by directors to accomplish better results. Just powerful administration can finish the task on time, inside spending plan, and with agreeable results.

Project Scheduling

In venture administration, a timetable comprises of a rundown of an undertaking's terminal components with proposed begin and complete dates. Terminal components are the most reduced component in a calendar, which is not further subdivided. Those things are frequently evaluated as far as asset prerequisites, spending plan and span, connected by conditions and booked.

The outlining methods are the booking apparatuses of the venture organizer. Indeed, even the least difficult undertaking ought to be diagrammed with the goal that advancement can be measured. The Gantt diagram is successful in straightforward undertakings, particularly when the interrelationships among occasions are not

very perplexing. Confused booking typically requires a PERT diagram.

A timetable must be adaptable in light of the fact that unforeseen occasions may happen that may influence the calendar of advancement of the framework. At times do frameworks ventures meet the first timetable at every point of reference. This doesn't infer that calendars are made to be broken, however a timetable can't be rigid to the point that when the unforeseen happens, consequent occasions can't be rescheduled.

A calendar has two essential capacities, it is both an arrangement and a gadget for measuring progress. The key strides in a timetable are called turning points, or checkpoints. As the venture advances, the date on which every turning point is finished is contrasted and the date for which it was anticipated. In any undertaking, incessant advancement audits occur in which the status of occasions is accounted for and assessed.

At the point when a venture is behind timetable, restorative strides must be taken. Setting up points of reference is insignificant unless the task supervisor can uphold adherence to plan. Implementation is an ordinary administrative obligation. On the off chance that a task pioneer can't uphold a calendar, another person ought to lead

the undertaking. The accompanying are assortment of alternatives that are interested in the task pioneer:

- Increase the financial backing.
- Increase labor as extra minutes or extra individuals.
- Add gear.
- Change needs.
- Replace the individual dependable.

GANTT CHART OF THE ACTIVITY

A Gantt diagram is a kind of bar outline, created by Henry Gantt, that represents an undertaking plan. Gantt graphs delineate the begin and complete dates of the terminal components and outline components of a venture. Terminal components and rundown components include the work breakdown structure of the undertaking. Some Gantt graphs likewise demonstrate the reliance (i.e., priority system) connections between exercises.

Gantt diagrams are helpful devices for arranging and planning ventures.

Gantt outlines permit you to evaluate to what extent a task ought to take.

- Gantt outlines lay the request in which undertakings should be done.
- Gantt graphs deal with the conditions between errands.
- Gantt graphs decide the assets required.
- Gantt graphs are helpful apparatuses when a venture is under way.
- Gantt graphs screen progress. You can quickly see what ought to have been accomplished at a point in time.
- Gantt graphs permit you to perceive how medicinal activity may bring the task back on course.

ADVANCED HOSPITAL MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

TASKS	Apr 1'st &2' nd Wee k	Apr3' rd & 4'th Week	May 1'st & 2'n d Wee k	Jun 3'rd - Jul y 1'st Wee k	Jul y 2'n d & Aug t 3'rd Wee k	Aug 4'rd & Sep t 1'st Wee k	Sep t 1'st & Sep t 3'rd Wee k	Sep t 3'rd & 4'th Wee k	Sep t 4'th Wee k
Problem Analysis	Day 1-12 12 Day s								
Analysis of Existing Systems like the proposed on		Day 13-22 10 Days							
Selection & Learning the S/W To be used			Day s 23- 32 10 Day s						
Understand ing Database				Day s 33- 47 15 Day s					
Coding					Day s 48- 62 15 day s				

ADVANCED HOSPITAL MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

Page Designing						Days 63-72 10 days			
Testing							Days 73-82 10 Days		
Evaluation								Days- 83-92 10 Days	
Implementation									Days 93-98 6 Days

PERT CHART

The list of tasks and events is networked in **PERT** chart in above figure. The arrow length is not significant, but the sequence and interconnections must give a true picture of the precedence of activities to be completed. The numbers on the activity lines are the time (in week) required between events.

Duration (in weeks) $2 + 3 + 1 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 1 + 1 = 16$
weeks

The **critical path** is the longest path through the network. No. task on the critical path can be held up without delaying the start of the next tasks and, ultimately, the completion of the project. So the critical path determines the project completion date.

SOFTWARE REQUIREMENTS SPECIFICATION

SRS is programming prerequisite particular it contains the s/w necessity subtle elements like what is front-end innovation, backend innovation, os and equipment engineering of the task.

SRS remains for Software Requirement Specification. It sets up the premise for assention amongst clients and temporary workers or suppliers on what the product item is relied upon to do, and in addition what it is not anticipated that would do.

A portion of the components of SRS are –

- It sets allows a thorough evaluation of prerequisites before configuration can start.
- It sets the premise for programming outline, test, organization, preparing and so on. It additionally sets pre-imperative for a decent outline however it is insufficient.
- It sets premise for programming upgrade and upkeep.
- It sets Basis for Project arranges like Scheduling and Estimation.

Subsequently, SRS ought to be reliable, right, unambiguous and complete, record. The designer of the framework can get ready SRS after point by point correspondence with the client. A SRS plainly characterizes the accompanying:

- External Interfaces of the framework: They recognize the data which is to stream 'from and to' to the framework.
- Functional and non-practical prerequisites of the framework. They remain for the finding of run time necessities.
- Design requirements:

The SRS blueprint is :

1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose

1.2 Scope

1.3 Definitions, acronyms, and abbreviations

1.4 References

1.5 Overview

2. Overall description

2.1 Product perspective

2.2 Product functions

2.3 User characteristics

2.4 Constraints

2.5 Assumptions and dependencies

3. Specific requirements

3.1 External Interfaces

3.2 Functional requirements

3.3 Performance requirements

3.4 Logical Database requirements

3.5 Design Constraints

3.6 Software system attributes

3.7 Organising the specific requirements

3.8 Additional Comments

4. Supporting information

2.1 Table of contents and index

2.2 Appendixes

The necessities gathering system is fortified and focused especially on programming. To appreciate the method for the program(s) to be manufactured, the item build ("analyst") must grasp the information space for the item, and required limit, behavior, execution, and interface. Necessities for both the system and the item are chronicled and investigated with the customer.

Layout

Programming diagram is truly a multi step set up that spotlights on four specific properties of a framework data structure, programming plan, interface representations, and procedural (algorithmic) unpretentious component. The arrangement system makes a translation of necessities into a representation of the item that can be gotten to for quality before coding begins. Like essentials, the layout is documented and ends up being a bit of the item setup.

Code Generation: -

The framework must be deciphered into a machine-important structure. The code period step plays out this task. If design is performed in a bare essential manner, code time can be capable carelessly.

Testing: -

At the point when code has been made, program testing begins. The testing system focuses on the wise internals of the item, ensuring that the entirety of what decrees have been attempted and on the useful veneers, that is, guiding tests to uncover goofs and ensure that described information will thing bona fide results that agree with required results.

Waterfall Model

It is the least demanding, most settled and most extensively used system model. In this model, each time of the life cycle is done before the start of another stage. It is truly the principle outlining system of programming change.

The waterfall model gives a deliberate and successive way to deal with programming improvement and is superior to the construct and settle approach. In any case, in this model, complete necessities ought to be accessible at the season of beginning of the venture, yet in real practice, the prerequisites continue starting amid various stages. The water fall model can oblige the new necessities just in support stage. In addition, it doesn't fuse any sort of danger appraisal. In waterfall show, a working model of

programming is not accessible. Consequently, there is no techniques to judge the issues of programming in the middle of various stages.

A slight alteration of the waterfall model is a model with input. When programming is created and is operational, then the input to different stages might be given.

SOFTWARE ENGINEERING PARADIGM

Straight Sequential Model has been utilized as a part of doing this anticipate work. The Linear Sequential Model is the most seasoned and the most broadly utilized worldview for Software Engineering. Straight Sequential Model is called now and again the Classic Life Cycle or the Waterfall Model.

The Linear Sequential Model recommends an efficient, Sequential way to deal with programming advancement that starts at the

framework level and advances through Analysis, Design, Coding, Testing and Support.

Linear Sequential Model contains the following activities:

System / Information Engineering and Modelling: -

Since programming is dependably part of a bigger framework (or business), work starts by setting up necessities for all framework components and after that assigning some subset of these prerequisites to programming. This framework perspective is vital when programming must communicate with different components, for example, equipment, individuals and database. Framework building and investigation incorporate necessities gathering at the framework level with a little measure of top-level outline and examination. Data designing envelops prerequisites gathering at the vital business level and at the business territory level.

In this anticipate, first I become acquainted with how the handling is done in the informal community framework. When I had acknowledged this anticipate the object is to create programming that ought to helps to produce the report. The product will serve them as a mechanized framework in playing out all the operation of the Online Vehicle Showroom System. Before beginning this anticipate or framework there are some data's required, they are:

1. First one is that comprehend about the working instrument of The social site.
2. Find out what sort of usefulness ought to be embraced by the proposed venture.
3. Which sort equipment and programming stage will be most reasonable for the proposed venture?

As the proposition framework was being kept up onto the type of paper based, writing identifying with this framework was accessible in the types of different reports. Different reports were accessible to gather information about the weakness of the current framework. The framework gives data that how the work is being done and how information are kept up which are helpful for the client, what changes should be made.

❖ **Requirement specification**

Issue illuminations for this situation are a great deal more troublesome. In either case, before any further strides can be taken, the undertaking demands must be unmistakably states. This stage (beginning study) includes assessing regardless of whether an advancement task is advantageous. Issues with the current mechanized or manual framework are distinguished, and in addition the advantages and expenses of an option

framework. In the event that the advantages appear to by and large the expenses (particularly when contrasted and contending ventures), a green sign might be given to proceed with the task, and nitty gritty plans and timetables are drafted for making the framework a reality.

The proposed answer for the client's issue may include something between sensational change (totally new framework) and slight change to the present framework. On the off chance that the present framework is manual and a PC framework is proposed, the improvement undertaking will most likely be huge.

CHEPTER-5

ANALYSIS DESIGN

5.1 DATA FLOW DIAGRAM

The Data stream graph can be clarified as the different levels demonstrating the individual unpredictability in the every level of the framework and gives a point by point clarification in the further levels that are tailing them.

LEVEL 0

At first in the main level of the Data stream the level 0 clarifies the essential blueprint of the framework. The end-client sends the parcels to the framework to decide the source and destination address. The chart set apart as the 0 speaks to the complete Packet watching framework which essentially speaks to the fundamental operation that is being performed by it in the underlying level.

LEVEL 1

The level 1 of the Data stream graph given clarifies in insight about the Packet watching framework which was set apart as 0 in the past level. In this level the end-client who passes the solicitation for the framework goes into the main procedure, the catching procedure and after that to the handling module. Subsequent to preparing the parcels it was send for putting away.

LEVEL 2

The level 2 gives the reasonable clarification about the entire framework. In this level first we need to choose the bundle and perform test over that chose parcels. At that point recognize the end location of the bundle and send that parcel for handling. In the wake of handling the bundle it was send to the personality content. At that point send the handled parcel for putting away and show the source and destination addresses.

DATA FLOW DIAGRAMS

Context Level DFD

First Level DFD For Admin

First Level DFD For Doctor

First Level DFD For Patient

Second level DFD

2nd Level DFD for Admin Module

CHEPTER-6

CODING

Connection

```
<?php

$hostname = "localhost:3306"; //sql port no
$username = "root"; //user name
$password = "root"; //password

$dbhandle = mysql_connect($hostname, $username, $password)
    or die("Unable to connect to MySQL");

//select a database
$dbselected = mysql_select_db("dbhospital", $dbhandle) //database name
    or die("Could not select examples");

error_reporting(0);
?>
```

New Registration

```
<!DOCTYPE HTML PUBLIC "-//W3C//DTD HTML 4.01 Transitional//EN">
<?php
error_reporting(0);
ob_start();
session_start();
?>
<html>
    <head>
        <meta http-equiv="Content-Type" content="text/html; charset=UTF-8">
        <link href="css/headerbar.css" rel="Stylesheet" type="text/css">
        <script type="text/javascript" src="js/scw.js"></script>
        <title>Railway Reservation Sytem</title>
        <script type="text/javascript">
            function validate(){
```

```
var name = document.getElementById("txt_name").value;
if(name == ""){
    alert('Name field cannot be blank. ');
    return false;
}
var dob = document.getElementById("txt_dob").value;
if(dob == ""){
    alert('Please Enter Your Date Of Birth. ');
    return false;
}
var gender = document.getElementById("txt_gndr").value;
if(gender=="na")
{
    alert('Please select a gender');
    return false;
}
var phone = document.getElementById("txt_phone").value;
if(phone == ""){
    alert('Please Enter Your Contact Number. ');
    return false;
}
var Contact_as = document.getElementById("txt_cntas").value;
if(Contact_as == ""){
    alert('Please Select Contact As. ');
    return false;
}
var Email = document.getElementById("txt_eml").value;
if(Email == ""){
    alert('Please Enter Your Email. ');
    return false;
}
var a = document.getElementById("txt_pass").value;
if(a == ""){
```

```

        alert('Password field cannot be blank. ');
        return false;
    }
    var b = document.getElementById("txtcpass").value;
    if(b == ""){
        alert('Confirm Password field cannot be blank. ');
        return false;
    }
    if(a != b){
        alert('Confirm password does not matched. ');
        return false;
    }
}

//check for Integer
function checkInteger(i)
{
    if(i.value.length>0)
    {
        i.value = i.value.replace(/[^d]+/g, "");
    }
}
}
</script>
</head>
<body>
    <table cellpadding="0" rules="none" frame="box" cellspacing="0" border="0"
width="100%">
        <tr>
            <td>
                <table cellpadding="0" cellspacing="0" border="0" bgcolor="white"
width="950px" align="center">

```

ADVANCED HOSPITAL MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

```
<tr height="150px">
  <td width="200px" height="150px">
    
  </td>
  <td width="800px" height="150px">
    
  </td>
</tr>
<tr>
  <td colspan="2">
    <?php
include("home_links.php");
?>
  </td>
</tr>
<tr>
  <td>
    <?php include("side_bar.php"); ?>
  </td>
  <td>
    <form id="frm" action="sourcecode/registration.php"
method="post">
      <table align="center" cellpadding="5" cellspacing="5">
        <tr>
          <td class="heading" colspan="2">Registration</td>
        </tr>
        <tr>
          <td colspan="2" valign="middle" align="center">
            <?php
            if ($_SESSION['MSG'] != "") {
```

ADVANCED HOSPITAL MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

```
        echo '<div class="msgbox">' . $_SESSION['MSG'] .
'</div>';

        $_SESSION['MSG'] = "";
    }
    ?>
</td>
</tr>
<tr>
    <td >Name:</td>
    <td><input type="text" id="txt_name" name="txt_name"
style="width: 250px; height: 25px;"></td>
</tr>
<tr>
    <td >DOB:</td>
    <td><input type="text" id="txt_dob"
name="txt_dob"style="width: 250px; height: 25px;" readonly
onclick="scwShow(this,event)"></td>
</tr>
<tr>
    <td >Gender:</td>
    <td>
        <select id="txt_gndr" name="txt_gndr" style="width:
250px; height: 25px;">
            <option value="select"> - - - -Select - - - - </option>
            <option value="Male">Male</option>
            <option value="Female">Female</option>
        </select>
    </td>
</tr>
<tr>
    <td >Phone</td>
    <td><input type="text" id="txt_phone"
name="txt_phone" style="width: 250px; height: 25px;"
onkeyup="checkInteger(this,value)"></td>
```

ADVANCED HOSPITAL MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

```
</tr>
<tr>
  <td >Location:</td>
  <td><input type="text" id="txt_adrs" name="txt_adrs"
style="width: 250px; height: 25px;"></td>
</tr>
<tr>
  <td >City:</td>
  <td><input type="text" id="txt_cntas" name="txt_cntas"
style="width: 250px; height: 25px;"></td>
</tr>
<tr>
  <td >Login Name:</td>
  <td><input type="text" id="txt_eml" name="txt_eml"
style="width: 250px; height: 25px;"></td>
</tr>
<tr>
  <td >Password:</td>
  <td><input type="password" id="txt_pass"
name="txt_pass" style="width: 250px; height: 25px;"></td>
</tr>
<tr>
  <td >Confirm Password:</td>
  <td><input type="password" id="txtcpass"
name="txtcpass" style="width: 250px; height: 25px;"></td>
</tr>
<tr>
  <td align="center" colspan="2">
    <input type="submit" class="button" value="Submit"
onclick="return validate();">
    <input type="reset" class="button" value="Reset">
  </td>
</tr>
```

```
        </table>
    </form>

    </td>
</tr>
<tr>
    <td colspan="2" class="footer" align="center">Design & Develop
By : Railway Reservation Sytem@Team</td>
</tr>
</table>

</td>
</tr>
</table>
</body>
</html>
```

Bill.php

```
`<?php
error_reporting(0);
ob_start();
session_start();
header("Pragma: no-cache");
header("Cache: no-cahce");
$user_id = "";
$user_id = $_SESSION['USERID'];
if ($user_id != "") {

    include_once "connection/dbconfig.php"; //Connection */
?>
<script type="text/javascript">
    function contact(i)
    {
```

```

if(i.value.length>0)
{
    i.value = i.value.replace(/[\^d]+/g, "");

}
}
function CheckForAlphabets(elem)
{
    var alphaExp = /^[a-z A-Z]+$/;
    if(elem.value.match(alphaExp)){
        return true;
    }else{
        alert("give alphabetic name ");
        return false;
    }
}
function mob()
{
    var rl=document.getElementById("txt_phone").value;
    if(rl.toString().length<10||rl.toString().length>10)
    {
        alert("Contact No. should be of ten digits");
        return false;
    }

}
</script>
<script type="text/javascript">
function valid() {
    //alert('calling');
    var reg = /^[A-Za-z0-9_-\.\.]+\@([A-Za-z0-9_-\.\.]+\.[A-Za-z]{2,4})$/;
    // var address = document.forms[form_id].elements[txtemail_id].value;
    var address = document.getElementById("txt_eml").value;
    if(reg.test(address) == false) {

```

```
        alert('Invalid Email Address');
        return false;
    }
}
</script>
<script type="text/javascript">
    function validate(){

        var name = document.getElementById("txt_name").value;
        if(name == ""){
            alert('Name field cannot be blank. ');
            return false;
        }
        var dob = document.getElementById("txt_dob").value;
        if(dob == ""){
            alert('Please Enter Your Date Of Birth. ');
            return false;
        }
        var gender = document.getElementById("txt_gndr").value;
        if(gender=="na")
        {
            alert('Please select a gender');
            return false;
        }
        var phone = document.getElementById("txt_phone").value;
        if(phone == ""){
            alert('Please Enter Your Contact Number. ');
            return false;
        }
        var Contact_as = document.getElementById("txt_cntas").value;
        if(Contact_as == ""){
            alert('Please Select Contact As. ');
            return false;
        }
    }
}
```

ADVANCED HOSPITAL MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

```
var Email = document.getElementById("txt_eml").value;
if(Email == ""){
    alert('Please Enter Your Email.');
```

```
    return false;
}
var a = document.getElementById("txt_pass").value;
if(a == ""){
    alert('Password field cannot be blank.');
```

```
    return false;
}
var b = document.getElementById("txtcpass").value;
if(b == ""){
    alert('Confirm Password field cannot be blank.');
```

```
    return false;
}
if(a != b){
    alert('Confirm password does not matched.');
```

```
    return false;
}
}

//check for Integer
function checkInteger(i)
{
    if(i.value.length>0)
    {
        i.value = i.value.replace(/[^d]+/g, "");
    }
}
}
</script>
<!DOCTYPE HTML PUBLIC "-//W3C//DTD HTML 4.01 Transitional//EN">
```

ADVANCED HOSPITAL MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

```
<html>
  <head>
    <meta http-equiv="Content-Type" content="text/html; charset=UTF-8">
    <link href="css/headerbar.css" rel="Stylesheet" type="text/css">
    <link href="Style-Sheet/style-sheet.css" type="text/css" rel="stylesheet"/>
    <link href="Style-Sheet/Corner.css" type="text/css" rel="stylesheet"/>
    <script src="JavaScript/crawler.js" type="text/javascript"></script>
    <script type="text/javascript" src="js/scw.js"></script>
    <title>Hospital Management System</title>
  </head>
  <body>
    <table cellpadding="0" rules="none" frame="box" cellspacing="0" border="0"
width="100%">
      <tr>
        <td>
          <table cellpadding="0" cellspacing="0" border="0" bgcolor="white"
width="950px" align="center">
            <tr height="150px">

              <td width="200px" height="150px">
                
              </td>
              <td width="800px" height="150px">
                <?php include("Slide.php"); ?>
              </td>
            </tr>
            <tr>
              <td colspan="2">
                <?php
                  include("header.php");
                ?>
              </td>
            </tr>
          </table>
        </td>
      </tr>
    </table>
  </body>
</html>
```

```

<tr>
  <td valign="top">
    <?php include("leftmenu.php"); ?>
  </td>
  <td height="500" valign="top" style="padding-left: 50px;">
    <form id="frm" action="sourcecode/bill.php" method="post">
      <table align="center" cellpadding="5" cellspacing="5">
        <tr>
          <td class="heading" colspan="2">Bill Payment...</td>
        </tr>
        <tr>
          <td colspan="2" valign="middle" align="center">
            <?php
            if ($_SESSION['MSG'] != "") {
              echo '<div class="msgbox">' . $_SESSION['MSG'] .
'</div>';
              $_SESSION['MSG'] = "";
            }
            ?>
          </td>
        </tr>
        <tr>
          <td >Patient Id:</td>
          <td>
            <select style="width:225px;" name="pid" id="pid"
class="combo">
              <option value="-1">--Select--</option>
              <?php
              $result = mysql_query("select * from
patientregistration");
              while ($row = mysql_fetch_array($result)) {
                $ctr++;
              }
            ?>
          </td>
        </tr>
      </table>
    </form>
  </td>
</tr>

```

ADVANCED HOSPITAL MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

```
<option value="<?php echo $row['patientid'];
?>"><?php echo $row['patientid']; ?></option>
<?php
}
?>
</select>
</td> </tr>
<tr>
<td >Patient Name:</td>
<td><input type="text" id="txt_name" name="txt_name"
style="width: 250px; height: 25px;"></td>
</tr>
<tr>
<td >DOB:</td>
<td><input type="text" id="txt_dob"
name="txt_dob" style="width: 250px; height: 25px;" readonly
onclick="scwShow(this,event)"></td>
</tr>
<tr>
<td >Gender:</td>
<td>
<select id="txt_gndr" name="txt_gndr" style="width:
250px; height: 25px;">
<option value="select"> - - - -Select - - - - </option>
<option value="Male">Male</option>
<option value="Female">Female</option>
</select>
</td>
</tr>
<tr>
<td >Phone</td>
<td><input type="text" id="txt_phone"
name="txt_phone" style="width: 250px; height: 25px;"
onkeyup="checkInteger(this,value)"></td>
```

ADVANCED HOSPITAL MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

```
</tr>
<tr>
  <td >Location:</td>
  <td><input type="text" id="txt_adrs" name="txt_adrs"
style="width: 250px; height: 25px;"></td>
</tr>
<tr>
  <td >City:</td>
  <td><input type="text" id="txt_cntas" name="txt_cntas"
style="width: 250px; height: 25px;"></td>
</tr>
<tr>
  <td >Email:</td>
  <td><input type="text" id="txt_eml" name="txt_eml"
style="width: 250px; height: 25px;" onblur="valid()"></td>
</tr>
<tr>
  <td >Dieases Type:</td>
  <td class="text">
    <select id="cmbdieades" name="cmbdieades"
style="width: 180px">
      <option value="Select"> - - - - - Select- - - - -
- - - </option>
      <option value="ENT">ENT</option>
      <option value="DENTRAL">DENTRAL</option>
      <option
value="PHYSICIAN">PHYSICIAN</option>
    </select>
  </td> </tr>
<tr>
  <td >Floor Type:</td>
  <td class="text">
```

ADVANCED HOSPITAL MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

```
<select id="cmbroom" name="cmbroom" style="width:
180px">
    <option value="Select">----- Select-----
--- </option>
    <option value="First Floor">First Floor</option>
    <option value="Second Floor">Second
Floor</option>
</select>
</td> </tr>
<tr>
    <td >NO Of Days:</td>
    <td><input type="text" id="txtroomno"
name="txtroomno" style="width: 250px; height: 25px;"></td>
</tr>
<tr>
    <td >Admitting Date:</td>
    <td><input type="text" id="txtadate"
name="txtadate" style="width: 250px; height: 25px;" readonly
onclick="scwShow(this,event)"></td>
</tr>
<tr>
    <td >Discharge Date:</td>
    <td><input type="text" id="txtddate"
name="txtddate" style="width: 250px; height: 25px;" readonly
onclick="scwShow(this,event)"></td>
</tr>
<tr>
    <td >Consultant Doctor:</td>
    <td>
        <select style="width:225px;" name="cmbdoctor"
id="cmbdoctor" class="combo">
            <option value="-1">--Select--</option>
</select>
</td>
</tr>
</table>
</body>
</html>
<?php
```

ADVANCED HOSPITAL MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

```
$result = mysql_query("select * from doctorregis");
while ($row = mysql_fetch_array($result)) {
    $ctr++;
    ?>
    <option value="<?php echo $row['name'];
?>"><?php echo $row['name']; ?></option>
    <?php
    }
    ?>
</select>
</td> </tr>

<tr>
<td >Discription:</td>
<td><textarea rows="4" cols="25" id="txtdis"
name="txtdis"></textarea></td>
</tr>
<tr>
<td >Total:</td>
<td><input type="text" id="txttotal" name="txttotal"
style="width: 250px; height: 25px;"></td>
</tr>

<tr>
<td align="center" colspan="2">
<input type="submit" class="button" value="Submit"
onclick="return validate();">
<input type="reset" class="button" value="Reset">
</td>
</tr>
</table>
</form>
</td>
</tr>
```

```
<tr>
    <td colspan="2" class="footer" align="center">Design & Develop
By :Hospital Management System@Team</td>
</tr>
</table>
```

```
</td>
</tr>
</table>
</body>
</html>
```

```
<?php
    } else {
        $_SESSION['MSG'] = "You must be login"; //set
message in sessiong
        header("location:index.php");
    }
?>
```

DoctorHome.php

```
<?php
error_reporting(0);
ob_start();
session_start();
header("Pragma: no-cache");
header("Cache: no-cahce");
$user_id = "";
$user_id = $_SESSION['USERID'];
if ($user_id != "") {
```

ADVANCED HOSPITAL MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

```
include_once "connection/dbconfig.php"; //Connection */
?>

<!DOCTYPE HTML PUBLIC "-//W3C//DTD HTML 4.01 Transitional//EN">
<html>
  <head>
    <meta http-equiv="Content-Type" content="text/html; charset=UTF-8">
    <link href="css/headerbar.css" rel="Stylesheet" type="text/css">
    <link href="Style-Sheet/style-sheet.css" type="text/css" rel="stylesheet"/>
    <link href="Style-Sheet/Corner.css" type="text/css" rel="stylesheet"/>
    <script src="JavaScript/crawler.js" type="text/javascript"></script>
    <title>Hospital Management System</title>
  </head>
  <body>
    <table cellpadding="0" rules="none" frame="box" cellspacing="0"
border="0" width="100%">
      <tr>
        <td>
          <table cellpadding="0" cellspacing="0" border="0" bgcolor="white"
width="950px" align="center">
            <tr height="150px">

              <td width="200px" height="150px">
                
              </td>
              <td width="800px" height="150px">
                <?php include("Slide.php"); ?>
              </td>
            </tr>
            <tr>
              <td colspan="2">
                <?php
include("header.php");
```

ADVANCED HOSPITAL MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

```
        ?>
    </td>
</tr>
<tr>
    <td valign="top">
        <?php include("leftmenu.php"); ?>
    </td>
    <td height="500" valign="top" style="padding-left: 50px;">
        <form action="sourcecode/profilesetting.php" method="post">
            <table cellpadding="5" cellspacing="5" border="0">
                <tr>
                    <td class="heading" colspan="2">Welcome Mr. <?php
echo $_SESSION['NAME'];?>.</td>
                </tr>
            </table>
        </form>
    </td>
</tr>
<tr>
    <td colspan="2" class="footer" align="center">Design &
Develop By :Hospital Management System@Team</td>
</tr>
</table>

</td>
</tr>
</table>
</body>
</html>
<?php
        } else {
            $_SESSION['MSG'] = "You must be login"; //set
message in sessiong
```

```
        header("location:index.php");
    }
?>
```

Patient Registration.php

```
`<?php
error_reporting(0);
ob_start();
session_start();
header("Pragma: no-cache");
header("Cache: no-cahce");
$user_id = "";
$user_id = $_SESSION['USERID'];
if ($user_id != "") {

    include_once "connection/dbconfig.php"; //Connection */
?>
<script type="text/javascript">
    function contact(i)
    {
        if(i.value.length>0)
        {
            i.value = i.value.replace(/[\^d]+/g, "");
        }
    }
    function CheckForAlphabets(elem)
    {
        var alphaExp = /^[a-z A-Z]+$/;
        if(elem.value.match(alphaExp)){
            return true;
        }else{
            alert("give alphabetic name ");

```

```

        return false;
    }
}
function mob()
{
    var rl=document.getElementById("txt_phone").value;
    if(rl.toString().length<10||rl.toString().length>10)
    {
        alert("Contact No. should be of ten digits");
        return false;
    }

}
</script>
<script type="text/javascript">
    function valid() {
        //alert('calling');
        var reg = /^[A-Za-z0-9_\-\.]+\@([A-Za-z0-9_\-\.]+\.[A-Za-z]{2,4})$/;
        // var address = document.forms[form_id].elements[txtemail_id].value;
        var address = document.getElementById('txt_eml').value;
        if(reg.test(address) == false) {
            alert('Invalid Email Address');
            return false;
        }
    }
</script>

<!DOCTYPE HTML PUBLIC "-//W3C//DTD HTML 4.01 Transitional//EN">
<html>
    <head>
        <meta http-equiv="Content-Type" content="text/html; charset=UTF-8">
        <link href="css/headerbar.css" rel="Stylesheet" type="text/css">
        <link href="Style-Sheet/style-sheet.css" type="text/css" rel="stylesheet"/>
        <link href="Style-Sheet/Corner.css" type="text/css" rel="stylesheet"/>

```

ADVANCED HOSPITAL MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

```
<script src="JavaScript/crawler.js" type="text/javascript"></script>
<script type="text/javascript" src="js/scw.js"></script>
<title>Hospital Management System</title>
</head>
<body>
  <table cellpadding="0" rules="none" frame="box" cellspacing="0" border="0"
width="100%">
  <tr>
    <td>
      <table cellpadding="0" cellspacing="0" border="0" bgcolor="white"
width="950px" align="center">
        <tr height="150px">

          <td width="200px" height="150px">
            
          </td>
          <td width="800px" height="150px">
            <?php include("Slide.php"); ?>
          </td>
        </tr>
        <tr>
          <td colspan="2">
            <?php
              include("header.php");
            ?>
          </td>
        </tr>
        <tr>
          <td valign="top">
            <?php include("leftmenu.php"); ?>
          </td>
          <td height="500" valign="top" style="padding-left: 50px;">
```

ADVANCED HOSPITAL MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

```
<form id="frm" action="sourcecode/patientregistration.php"
method="post">
    <table align="center" cellpadding="5" cellspacing="5">
        <tr>
            <td class="heading" colspan="2">Registration</td>
        </tr>
        <?php
            // $query = ("select * from student order by
(StudentId)desc limit 1 ");
            //$r = mysql_query($query);
            $result = mysql_query("select * from
patientregistration order by (patientid)desc limit 1");
            while ($row = mysql_fetch_array($result)) {
                //echo "abc";
                $num = $row['patientid'];
                //echo $num;
                $n = (int) $num;
                //echo $n;
                //$num = $num + 1;
                $patientid = $n + 1;
            }
            ?>
            <tr>
                <td>Patient&nbsp;Id:</td>
                <td><input type="text" size="25" id="sid"
name="sid" readonly value="<?php echo $patientid ?>"></td>
            </tr>
            <tr>
                <td >Name:</td>
                <td><input type="text" id="txt_name" name="txt_name"
style="width: 250px; height: 25px;"></td>
```

ADVANCED HOSPITAL MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

```
</tr>
<tr>
  <td >DOB:</td>
  <td><input type="text" id="txt_dob"
name="txt_dob"style="width: 250px; height: 25px;" readonly
onclick="scwShow(this,event)"></td>
</tr>
<tr>
  <td >Gender:</td>
  <td>
    <select id="txt_gndr" name="txt_gndr" style="width:
250px; height: 25px;">
      <option value="select"> - - - -Select - - - - </option>
      <option value="Male">Male</option>
      <option value="Female">Female</option>
    </select>
  </td>
</tr>
<tr>
  <td >Phone</td>
  <td><input type="text" id="txt_phone"
name="txt_phone" style="width: 250px; height: 25px;"
onkeyup="checkInteger(this,value)"></td>
</tr>
<tr>
  <td >Location:</td>
  <td><input type="text" id="txt_adrs" name="txt_adrs"
style="width: 250px; height: 25px;"></td>
</tr>
<tr>
  <td >City:</td>
  <td><input type="text" id="txt_cntas" name="txt_cntas"
style="width: 250px; height: 25px;"></td>
</tr>
```

ADVANCED HOSPITAL MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

```
<tr>
  <td >Email:</td>
  <td><input type="text" id="txt_eml" name="txt_eml"
style="width: 250px; height: 25px;" onblur="valid()"></td>
</tr>
<tr>
  <td >Dieases Type:</td>
  <td class="text">
    <select id="cmbdieades" name="cmbdieades"
style="width: 180px">
      <option value="Select"> - - - - - Select - - - - -
- - - </option>
      <option value="ENT">ENT</option>
      <option value="DENTRAL">DENTRAL</option>
      <option
value="PHYSICIAN">PHYSICIAN</option>
    </select>
  </td> </tr>
<tr>
  <td >Floor:</td>
  <td class="text">
    <select id="cmbroom" name="cmbroom" style="width:
180px">
      <option value="select"> - - - -Select - - - - </option>
      <option value="First Floor">First Floor</option>
      <option value="Second Floor">Second
Floor</option>
      <option value="Third Floor">Third Floor</option>
    </select>
  </td> </tr>
<tr>
  <td >Room.:</td>
```

ADVANCED HOSPITAL MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

```
<td><input type="text" id="txtroomno"
name="txtroomno" style="width: 250px; height: 25px;"></td>
</tr>
<tr>
<td >Admitting Date:</td>
<td><input type="text" id="txtadate"
name="txtadate"style="width: 250px; height: 25px;" readonly
onclick="scwShow(this,event)"></td>
</tr>
<tr>
<td >Doctor:</td>
<td>
<select style="width:225px;" name="cmbdoctor"
id="cmbdoctor" class="combo">
<option value="-1">--Select--</option>
<?php
$result = mysql_query("select * from doctorregis");
while ($row = mysql_fetch_array($result)) {
    $ctr++;
    ?>
<option value="<?php echo $row['name'];
?>"><?php echo $row['name']; ?></option>
<?php
}
?>
</select>
</td>
</tr>
<tr>
<td align="center" colspan="2">
<input type="submit" class="button" value="Submit"
onclick="return validate();">
```

ADVANCED HOSPITAL MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

```
        <input type="reset" class="button" value="Reset">
    </td>
</tr>
</table>
</form>
</td>
</tr>
<tr>
    <td colspan="2" class="footer" align="center">Design &
Develop By :Hospital Management System@Team</td>
</tr>
</table>

</td>
</tr>
</table>
</body>
</html>
<?php
        } else {
            $_SESSION['MSG'] = "You must be login"; //set
message in sessiong
            header("location:index.php");
        }
?>
```

Room.php

```
<?php
error_reporting(0);
ob_start();
session_start();
header("Pragma: no-cache");
header("Cache: no-cahce");
```

ADVANCED HOSPITAL MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

```
$user_id = "";
$user_id = $_SESSION['USERID'];
if ($user_id != "") {

    include_once "connection/dbconfig.php"; //Connection */
?>

<!DOCTYPE HTML PUBLIC "-//W3C//DTD HTML 4.01 Transitional//EN">
<html>
  <head>
    <meta http-equiv="Content-Type" content="text/html; charset=UTF-8">
    <link href="css/headerbar.css" rel="Stylesheet" type="text/css">
    <link href="Style-Sheet/style-sheet.css" type="text/css" rel="stylesheet"/>
    <link href="Style-Sheet/Corner.css" type="text/css" rel="stylesheet"/>
    <script src="JavaScript/crawler.js" type="text/javascript"></script>
    <script type="text/javascript" src="js/scw.js"></script>
    <title>Hospital Management System</title>
  </head>
  <body>
    <table cellpadding="0" rules="none" frame="box" cellspacing="0" border="0"
width="100%">
      <tr>
        <td>
          <table cellpadding="0" cellspacing="0" border="0" bgcolor="white"
width="950px" align="center">
            <tr height="150px">

              <td width="200px" height="150px">
                
              </td>
              <td width="800px" height="150px">
                <?php include("Slide.php"); ?>
              </td>
            </tr>
          </table>
        </td>
      </tr>
    </table>
  </body>
</html>
```

```

</tr>
<tr>
  <td colspan="2">
    <?php
      include("header.php");
    ?>
  </td>
</tr>
<tr>
  <td valign="top">
    <?php include("leftmenu.php"); ?>
  </td>
  <td height="500" valign="top" style="padding-left: 50px;">
    <form id="frm" action="sourcecode/room.php" method="post">
      <table align="center" cellpadding="5" cellspacing="5">
        <tr>
          <td class="heading" colspan="2">Registration</td>
        </tr>
        <tr>
          <td >Floor:</td>
          <td>
            <select id="txtfloor" name="txtfloor" style="width:
250px; height: 25px;">
              <option value="select"> - - - -Select - - - - </option>
              <option value="First Floor">First Floor</option>
              <option value="Second Floor">Second
Floor</option>
            </select>
          </td>
        </tr>
        <tr>
          <td >Room No:</td>
          <td>

```

ADVANCED HOSPITAL MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

```
<select id="txtro" name="txtro" style="width: 250px;
height: 25px;">
    <option value="select"> - - - -Select - - - - </option>
    <option value="1">1</option>
    <option value="2">2</option>
    <option value="3">3</option>
    <option value="4">4</option>
    <option value="5">5</option>
    <option value="6">6</option>
    <option value="7">7</option>
    <option value="8">8</option>
    <option value="9">9</option>
    <option value="10">10</option>

</select>
</td> </tr>

<tr>
<td >Status:</td>
<td class="text">
    <select id="txtstatus" name="txtstatus" style="width:
180px">
        <option value="Select"> - - - - - Select- - - - -
- - - </option>
        <option value="Booked">Booked</option>
        <option value="Avalible">Avalible</option>

    </select>
</td> </tr>

<tr>
<td align="center" colspan="2">
    <input type="submit" class="button" value="Submit"
onclick="return validate();">
```

ADVANCED HOSPITAL MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

```
        <input type="reset" class="button" value="Reset">
    </td>
</tr>
</table>
</form>
</td>
</tr>

<tr>
    <td colspan="2" class="footer" align="center">Design & Develop
By :Hospital Management System@Team</td>
</tr>
</table>

</td>
</tr>
</table>
</body>
</html>
<?php
    } else {
        $_SESSION['MSG'] = "You must be login"; //set message in
sessiong
        header("location:index.php");
    }
?>
```

RoomList.php

```
<?php
error_reporting(0);
ob_start();
session_start();
```

ADVANCED HOSPITAL MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

```
header("Pragma: no-cache");
header("Cache: no-cache");
$user_id = "";
$user_id = $_SESSION['USERID'];
if ($user_id != "") {

    include_once "connection/dbconfig.php";
//Connection */
?>

<!DOCTYPE HTML PUBLIC "-//W3C//DTD HTML
4.01 Transitional//EN">
<html>
<head>
<meta http-equiv="Content-Type"
content="text/html; charset=UTF-8">
<link href="css/headerbar.css" rel="stylesheet"
type="text/css">
<link href="Style-Sheet/style-sheet.css"
type="text/css" rel="stylesheet"/>
<link href="Style-Sheet/Corner.css"
type="text/css" rel="stylesheet"/>
<script src="JavaScript/crawler.js"
type="text/javascript"></script>
<script type="text/javascript"
src="js/scw.js"></script>
<title>Hospital Management System</title>
</head>
<body>
<table cellpadding="0" rules="none" frame="box"
cellspacing="0" border="0" width="100%">
<tr>
<td>
```

ADVANCED HOSPITAL MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

```
<table cellpadding="0" cellspacing="0"
border="0" bgcolor="white" width="950px" align="center">
  <tr height="150px">
    <td width="200px" height="150px">
      
    </td>
    <td width="800px" height="150px">
      <?php include("Slide.php"); ?>
    </td>
  </tr>
  <tr>
    <td colspan="2">
      <?php
include("header.php");
?>
    </td>
  </tr>
  <tr>
    <td valign="top">
      <?php include("leftmenu.php"); ?>
    </td>
    <td height="500" valign="top"
style="padding-left: 50px;">
      <div style="width:600px;
height:500px; overflow: auto;">
        <table width="100%"
border="0" cellpadding="4" cellspacing="4">
          <?php
include_once
"config.php";
```

ADVANCED HOSPITAL MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

```

                                $result =
mysql_query("select * from class");

                                while ($row =
mysql_fetch_array($result)) {
                                ?>
                                <tr>
                                <td>
                                <table
width="100%" cellpadding="8" cellspacing="8" class="b-
text">
                                <tr style="color:
#000" valign="top">
                                <td>Class</td>
                                <td
align="justify"><?php echo $row ['Class']; ?></td>
                                </tr>
                                <tr style="color:
#000" valign="top">
                                <td>Sec</td>
                                <td><?php
echo $row['Sec']; ?></td>
                                </tr>
                                <tr style="color:
#000" valign="top">
                                <td>Update</td>
                                <td><a
href="updateclass.php?id=<?php echo $row['id'];
?>"style="color:red;text-decoration:none">Update</a></td>
                                </tr>
                                </table>

```

ADVANCED HOSPITAL MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

```

        </td>
    </tr>
<?php
    }
?>
</table>
</div>
</td>
</tr>

<tr>
    <td colspan="2" class="footer"
align="center">Design & Develop By :Hospital Management
System@Team</td>
</tr>
</table>

</td>
</tr>
</table>
</body>
</html>
<?php
    } else {
        $_SESSION['MSG'] = "You must
be login"; //set message in sessiong
        header("location:index.php");
    }
?>
```

Index.php

```

<!DOCTYPE HTML PUBLIC "-//W3C//DTD HTML 4.01 Transitional//EN">
<html>
  <head>
    <meta http-equiv="Content-Type" content="text/html; charset=UTF-8">
    <link href="css/headerbar.css" rel="Stylesheet" type="text/css">
    <link href="Style-Sheet/style-sheet.css" type="text/css" rel="stylesheet"/>
    <link href="Style-Sheet/Corner.css" type="text/css" rel="stylesheet"/>
    <script src="JavaScript/crawler.js" type="text/javascript"></script>
    <title>Hospital Management System</title>
  </head>
  <body>
    <table cellpadding="0" rules="none" frame="box" cellspacing="0" border="0"
width="100%">
      <tr>
        <td>
          <table cellpadding="0" cellspacing="0" border="0" bgcolor="white"
width="950px" align="center">
            <tr height="150px">

              <td width="200px" height="150px">
                
              </td>
              <td width="800px" height="150px">
                <?php include("Slide.php"); ?>
              </td>
            </tr>
            <tr>
              <td colspan="2">
                <?php
                  include("home_links.php");
                ?>
              </td>
            </tr>
          </table>
        </td>
      </tr>
    </table>
  </body>
</html>

```

</td>

</tr>

<tr>

<td>

<?php include("menu.php"); ?>

</td>

<td valign="top">

<table>

<tr>

<td class="heading" colspan="3">About Project</td>

</tr>

<tr>

<td colspan="3">

There are numerous opportunities today than ever before to learn about your health and to take better care of yourself & your family. There are so many disciplines of medicines or treatment paradigm like ayurvedic, homeopathic, unani, chinese system, tibeten system, yoga, acupuncture and acupressure etc, that at particular moment it became confusing for the patient to decide what to go for. The site PATIENTS-CARE has been launched to help a common man / medical professional to take care of himself and his patient with different aspects of treatment.

A recent UK study found that 97% of consumers are willing to trust online reviews. Keith Pollard, Managing Director of Treatment Abroad says: “The Ratings and Reviews service is intended to inform patient choice. Patients need to be clued up on overseas medical treatment, and some may be apprehensive about the risks of travelling for treatment. Patients who have become ‘medical tourists’ generally tend to be extremely positive about their experience, so the addition of ratings and reviews on the site will further build patient confidence.”

</td>

</tr>

ADVANCED HOSPITAL MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

```
<tr>
  <td colspan="1">
    <table>
      <tr>
        <td>Our Inspiration</td>
      </tr>
      <tr>
        <td></td>
      </tr>
    </table>
  </td>
```

<td>Dr. Anil Vij is a practicing physician with 35 yrs. of experience in the field of medicine. He is a well known clinician with a practice based in Kathmandu. It was as a physician that he realized his own limitations when dealing with the enormous volume of medical literature on prescribing treatment to patients. This led him to develop software that could act as a clinician's true companion, aiding the clinician in writing a safe, fool-proof and first-rate prescription. Eight years of hard work saw his long cherished dream come to fruition in the form of PRESCRIPTION PAD, a state-of-the-art prescription writing software which contains everything a clinician might need in order to give his/her patients the very best of health-care.

In Dr. Vij's words, "Prescription writing is not merely putting down a few drug names on a piece of paper. It is an art mastered only after years of experience and hard work backed by sound knowledge of the basic subject." World over, there is stress on evidence-based medicine, best described as the conscientious, explicit and judicious use of current evidence in decision-making.</td>

```
</tr>
```

```
<tr>
  <td></td>
  <td></td>
```

```
</tr>

</table>

</td>
</tr>
<tr>
<td colspan="2" class="footer" align="center">Design & Develop
By : ANH HOSPITAL@Team</td>
</tr>
</table>

</td>
</tr>
</table>
</body>
</html>
```

SearchDoctor.php

```
<?php
error_reporting(0);
ob_start();
session_start();
header("Pragma: no-cache");
header("Cache: no-cahce");
$user_id = "";
$user_id = $_SESSION['USERID'];
if ($user_id != "") {

    include_once "connection/dbconfig.php"; //Connection */
?>
```

```

<!DOCTYPE HTML PUBLIC "-//W3C//DTD HTML 4.01 Transitional//EN">
<html>
  <head>
    <meta http-equiv="Content-Type" content="text/html; charset=UTF-8">
    <link href="css/headerbar.css" rel="Stylesheet" type="text/css">
    <link href="Style-Sheet/style-sheet.css" type="text/css" rel="stylesheet"/>
    <link href="Style-Sheet/Corner.css" type="text/css" rel="stylesheet"/>
    <script src="JavaScript/crawler.js" type="text/javascript"></script>
    <title>Hospital Management System</title>
    <script type="text/javascript">
function showUser(str)
{
if (str=="")
{
document.getElementById("txtHint").innerHTML="";
return;
}
if (window.XMLHttpRequest)
  {
  // code for IE7+, Firefox, Chrome, Opera, Safari
  xmlhttp=new XMLHttpRequest();
  }
else
  {
  // code for IE6, IE5
  xmlhttp=new ActiveXObject("Microsoft.XMLHTTP");
  }
xmlhttp.onreadystatechange=function()
{
if (xmlhttp.readyState==4 && xmlhttp.status==200)
{
document.getElementById("txtHint").innerHTML=xmlhttp.responseText;
}
}
xmlhttp.open("GET","getdoctor4.php?q="+str,true);
xmlhttp.send();

```

```

}
</script>

</head>
<body>
    <table cellpadding="0" rules="none" frame="box" cellspacing="0"
border="0" width="100%">
    <tr>
    <td>
        <table cellpadding="0" cellspacing="0" border="0" bgcolor="white"
width="950px" align="center">
        <tr height="150px">

            <td width="200px" height="150px">
                
            </td>
            <td width="800px" height="150px">
                <?php include("Slide.php"); ?>
            </td>
        </tr>
        <tr>
        <td colspan="2">
            <?php
            include("header.php");
            ?>
        </td>
        </tr>
        <tr>
        <td valign="top">
            <?php include("leftmenuuser.php"); ?>
        </td>
        <td height="500" valign="top" style="padding-left: 50px;">

```

ADVANCED HOSPITAL MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

```
<form id="frm" action="sourcecode/bloodregistration.php"
method="post">
<table align="center" cellpadding="5" cellspacing="5">
<tr>
<td class="heading" colspan="2">Search Blood
Group</td>
</tr>
<tr>
<td>Select Doctor Category:</td>
<td>
<select id="txtHint" name="txtHint" style="width:
250px; height: 25px;" name="users" onchange="showUser(this.value)">>
<option value="Select">----- Select-----
</option>
<option value="ENT">ENT</option>
<option
value="DENTRAL">DENTAL</option>
<option
value="PHYSICIAN">PHYSICIAN</option>
</select>
</td>
</tr>
<div id="txtHint"><b>Person info will be listed here.</b></div>
</table>
</form>
</td>
</tr>
```

```
<tr>
    <td colspan="2" class="footer" align="center">Design &
Develop By :Hospital Management System@Team</td>
</tr>
</table>
```

```
</td>
</tr>
</table>
</body>
</html>
```

```
<?php
    } else {
        $_SESSION['MSG'] = "You must be login"; //set
message in sessiong
        header("location:index.php");
    }
?>
```

HOSPITALLOGIN.PHP

```
<?php
error_reporting(0);

//clear cache
header('Cache-control: private'); // IE 6 FIX
// always modified
header('Last-Modified: ' . gmdate("D, d M Y H:i:s") . ' GMT');
// HTTP/1.1
header('Cache-Control: no-store, no-cache, must-revalidate');
header('Cache-Control: post-check=0, pre-check=0', false);
```

```
// HTTP/1.0
header('Pragma: no-cache');

//session management
ob_start(); //start object
session_start(); //start session
?>

<!DOCTYPE HTML PUBLIC "-//W3C//DTD HTML 4.01 Transitional//EN">
<html>
  <head>
    <meta http-equiv="Content-Type" content="text/html; charset=UTF-8">
    <link href="css/headerbar.css" rel="Stylesheet" type="text/css">
    <link href="Style-Sheet/style-sheet.css" type="text/css" rel="stylesheet"/>
    <link href="Style-Sheet/Corner.css" type="text/css" rel="stylesheet"/>
    <script src="JavaScript/crawler.js" type="text/javascript"></script>
    <title>Hospital Management System</title>
  </head>
  <body>
    <table cellpadding="0" rules="none" frame="box" cellspacing="0" border="0"
width="100%">
      <tr>
        <td>
          <table cellpadding="0" cellspacing="0" border="0" bgcolor="white"
width="950px" align="center">
            <tr height="150px">

              <td width="200px" height="150px">
                
              </td>
              <td width="800px" height="150px">
                <?php include("Slide.php"); ?>
              </td>
            </tr>
          </table>
        </td>
      </tr>
    </table>
  </body>
</html>
```

```

        </td>
    </tr>
    <tr>
        <td colspan="2">
            <?php
                include("home_links.php");
            ?>
        </td>
    </tr>
    <tr>
    <td>
        <form id="frm" action="sourcecode/login.php" method="post">
            <fieldset style="height: auto; width: 300px; padding: 10px;">
                <legend>Login</legend>
                <table align="center" cellpadding="5" cellspacing="5">
                    <tr>
                        <td colspan="2" valign="middle" align="center">
                            <?php
                                if ($_SESSION['MSG'] != "") {
                                    echo '<div class="msgbox">' . $_SESSION['MSG'] .
'</div>';
                                }
                                $_SESSION['MSG'] = "";
                            }
                            ?>
                        </td>
                    </tr>
                    <tr>
                        <td class="login-text">
                            Login As
                        </td>
                        <td class="login-text">
                            <input type="radio" name="rdologin" id="rdodoctor"
value="admin"/>&nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;Admin

```



```

        </tr>
    </table>
</body>
</html>

```

BILL.PHP

```

<?php

error_reporting(0);
ob_start();
session_start();
header("Pragma: no-cache");
header("Cache: no-cache");
include_once "../connection/dbconfig.php"; //Connection
$pid = $_POST['pid'];
$name = $_POST['txt_name'];
$dob = $_POST['txt_dob'];
$gender = $_POST['txt_gndr'];
$phone = $_POST['txt_phone'];
$address = $_POST['txt_adrs'];
$contact_as = $_POST['txt_cntas'];
$email = $_POST['txt_eml'];
$dtype = $_POST['cmbdieades'];
$rtype = $_POST['cmbroom'];
$rno = $_POST['txtroomno'];
$adate = $_POST['txtadate'];
$ddate = $_POST['txtddate'];
$doctor = $_POST['cmbdoctor'];
$discription = $_POST['txtdis'];
$total = $_POST['txttotal'];

$query = "insert into
billpayment(pid,name,dob,gender,phone,address,contact_as,email,diestype,rtype,rno,a

```

```

date,ddate,doctor,discription,total)
values('$pid','$name','$dob','$gender','$phone','$address','$contact_as','$email','$dtype'
,$rtype','$rno','$adate','$ddate','$doctor','$discription','$total)");

$r = mysql_query($query);
$num = (int) $r;
if ($num > 0) {
    $_SESSION['MSG'] = "Your information has been successfully submitted!!!";
    $_SESSION['NAME'] = $row ['pid'];
} else {
    $_SESSION['MSG'] = "Your information has not been submitted!!!";
}
header("location:../Thanku.php");
?>

```

DOCTORS.AVE.PHP

```

<?php

error_reporting(0);
ob_start();
session_start();
header("Pragma: no-cache");
header("Cache: no-cache");
include_once "../connection/dbconfig.php"; //Connection
$uid = $_SESSION['USERID'];

$uid = $_POST['txthidden'];
$name = $_POST['uname'];
$password = $_POST['pwd'];
$fname = $_POST['txtname'];
$lname = $_POST['txtlname'];
$gender = $_POST['cmbgender'];
$db = $_POST['txtdb'];
$number = $_POST['number'];

```

ADVANCED HOSPITAL MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

```
$email = $_POST['txtemail'];
$address = $_POST['txtaddress'];
$city = $_POST['cmbcity'];
$pin = $_POST['txtpin'];
$state = $_POST['txtstate'];
$country = $_POST['cmbcountry'];

$query = "insert into
staff(UserID,uname,pass,FirstName,LastName,Gender,DOB,ContactNo,EmailID,Address,
City,PinCode,State,Country)
values('$id','$name','$pass','$fname','$lname','$gender','$db','$number','$email','$pass','$address','$city','$pin','$state','$country')";

$r = mysql_query($query);
$num = (int) $r;
if ($num > 0) {
    $_SESSION['MSG'] = "Your information has been updated successfully.!!";
} else {
    $_SESSION['MSG'] = "Your information has not been updated successfully.!!";
}
header("location:../admin/NewDoctor.php");
?>
```

CHEPTER-7

TESTING

7.1 Testing Type

The testing of programming means measuring or getting to the product to decide the quality. Testing is a measuring instrument for programming quality with the unit of estimation being the quantity of imperfections found amid testing.

Testing exercises additionally accomplish programming quality. Testing is fundamental in the advancement of any framework programming. Testing is fundamental in the improvement of any product framework. Testing is with a specific end goal to get to what the framework really does and how very much anticipated that would burn through approximately 40% of advancement cost and time in testing keeping in mind the end goal to accomplish sensible quality levels.

Levels of Testing

- ❖ Unit Testing
- ❖ Component Integration Testing
- ❖ System Testing
- ❖ Acceptance Testing

Unit Testing

Unit testing includes the arrangement of tests performed for the most part by the software engineers preceding the reconciliation of the unit into a vast Program. This is the least level of testing and is

finished by the software engineer (Who creates it) who can test it in extraordinary point of interest. The capacity is done in disengagement. This is the place the most point by point examination of inner working of the individual unit is done.

Component Integration Testing

Whenever two or more tried segments are consolidated into a bigger structure, the testing procedure ought to search for mistakes in two ways:-

- In the interface between the parts
- The capacities, which can be performed by the new gathering

System Testing

After in joining testing is finished, the whole framework is tried as entirety. The utilitarian details or necessities determination are utilized to infer the experiment. At this level the framework testing searches for mistakes at last to-end utilitarian quality. Qualities, for example, execution, dependability,

Volume, stress resistance, ease of use, viability, security and so forth. Free analyzers can do this testing.

Acceptance Testing

After framework testing was finished, the framework was given over to the preparation area. Acknowledgment testing check the exchange from possession by the create to proprietorship by the clients. The acknowledgment test is diverse in nature to the advancement testing in three ways.

Firstly, it is an obligation of the tolerant area as opposed to improvement office (PC Center).

Besides, the motivation behind the acknowledgment testing was to see if the product is working as opposed to attempting to discover blunders.

Thirdly, it likewise incorporates the testing of client's specialization's working practices to guarantee that the PC programming will fit into administrative and managerial strategies of the concerned segment well.

Acknowledgment testing offered certainty to the client that the framework is prepared for operational use.

Security concern of computer where software is to be installed:

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exchange from possession by the create to proprietorship by the clients. The acknowledgment test is diverse in nature to the advancement testing in three ways.

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Acknowledgment testing offered certainty to the client that the framework is prepared for operational use.

Protecting the database

To secure the database, the accompanying strides are taken:-

- The server logged off and physically bolted up when it has not utilize.

- The database must be not shared on system. On the off chance that it is shared then change the properties.
- The database on prophet gives fine-grained consent system that permits ensuring specific database tables and segments. The table and section must be the limited to chairman of database so it is not overhaul by the any one.
- Using NTFS (NT document framework) security to further access to the database, it is utilized by utilizing ntfs authorization exchange to promote ensure delicate data.

TESTING OBJECTIVES

- No bugs blocks the execution of tasks
- System states are visible
- All factors affecting the output are visible
- Functional simplicity
- Distinct output is generated for each input

Debugging

Investigating happens as an outcome of effective testing. Investigating alludes to the procedure of distinguishing the reason for blemished conduct of a framework and addressive that issue. In less mind boggling terms-altering a bug. At the point when an experiment reveals an

Mistake, investigating is the procedure that outcomes in the expulsion of the blunder. The investigating procedure starts with the execution of an experiment. The investigating procedure endeavors to match manifestations with cause, in this manner prompting mistake rectification. The accompanying are two option results of the troubleshooting:

- the cause will be found and important activity, for example, adjustment or expulsion will be taken.
- The cause won't be found.

Attributes of bugs

1. The side effects subterranean insect the cause might be topographically remote. That is, the indications may show up in one a player in a project. While the cause may really be situated at a site that is far evacuated. Profoundly coupled project structures worsen this circumstance.
2. The manifestations may vanish (temporarily) when another blunder is associated.
3. the Symptom may really be brought about by non error(e.g, round-Off mistakes).
4. The side effects might be brought on by human blunder that is not effortlessly followed.

5. The indication might be an aftereffect of timing issues, as opposed to preparing issues.
6. It might be hard to precisely recreate information conditions(e.g, a continuous application in which info requesting is vague).
7. The manifestation might be irregular. This is especially regular in inserted frameworks that couple equipment and programming inseparably.
8. The manifestations might be because of causes that are appropriated over various errands running on various processors.

Validation Checks

There are six sorts of approvals:

- 1) Intrinsic control: In this control content Box, mark, drop down rundown are use for straightforward information and yield.
- 2)Rich control: Rich control have a two control `Add Repeater` and 'Date-book Control'.
- 3)Transfer Control: This control used to divert pages to next page like, Buttton, Hyperlink, linkButtons.
- 4) Validation control: There are six control:-
 - Required Filled Validator:- this control are utilizing for check the necessity is satisfy or not.

•Compare Validator:- This control are utilized for contrasting two values and help of controlToValidate and CompareToValidate.

The Type are taken in think about Validator are taking after: -

a) String

b) Integer

c) Double

d) Date

e) Currency

Administrator is utilized to determine a sort are taking after: -

a) Equal

b) No Equal

c) Greater Than

d) Greater than equivalent

e) Less than

f) Less than equivalent

- RangeValidator:- the reach validator is utilized to check if the estimation of control exists in an extent. The Range can be determined with the assistance of two control

a) Min

b) Max

- RegularExpressionValidator:- a pre indicated arrangement can excepted just in the event that they shape a part of a specific example, this for the most part happens in Phone no., charge card number or E-mail

Address from client. The telephone no. should be numeric. This is made conceivable by general Expression Validator Control. The example to which the worth must indicated in validationExpression property. The worth can be checked against small Pattern or

expressions by isolating every expressions with a channel Sign and encased expression in round section.

- CustomValidator:- custom validator control can be utilized to give validator on the off chance that all validator control are insufficient to approve the information.

- Validation Summary:- approval blunder message on the Web page can be showcase in two way. The blunders can either be shown as when the client line the control or outline of mistake can be show together. This control can be use to create, for example, summery. The mistake can be perspective as rundown projectile by setting show made.

CODE EFFICIENCY

MEASURES OF CODE EFFICIENCY

The code is laid out in light of the going with properties.

1. Uniqueness: The code structure must ensure that unparalleled estimation of the code with a singular hugeness is precisely associated with a give component or characteristic.

2. Expandability: The code structure are planned for in a way that it must mull over advancement of it's course of action of components or attributes, along these lines giving satisfactory space to the segment of new things with in each gathering.

3. Conciseness: The code requires the slightest possible number of positions to consolidate and describe everything.

4. Uniform size and design: Uniform size and association is significantly alluring in mechanized data get ready system. The extension of prefixes and increases to the root code should not be allowed especially as it is incongruent with the uniqueness need.

5. Simplicity: The codes are arranged clearly to understand and simple to apply.

6. Versatility: The code grants adjusting easily to reflect key changes in conditions, traits and relationship of the encoded substances. Such changes must result in a relating change in the code or coding structure.

7. Sortability: Reports are most critical for customer adequacy when sorted and presented in a destined game plan or demand. Regardless of the way that data must be sorted and collaged, the

representative code for the date does not ought to be in a sortable structure if it can be connected with another code that is sortable.

8. Stability: Codes that don't require to be a great part of the time redesigned moreover propel use efficiency. Solitary code assignments for a given component should be gained with a unimportant likelihood of ground either in the specific code or in the entire coding structure.

9. Meaningfulness: Code is critical. Code quality should reflect the traits of the coded substances, for instance, memory assistant highlights unless such a procedures results in inconsistency and determination.

OPTIMIZATION OF CODE

A decent program is not the one that tackles the expected issue alone yet the one that does it proficiently. A perfect compiler ought to create target code that is on a par with can be composed by hand made carefully to keep running on the objective machine in the most proficient way both as far as time of execution and memory necessities. The truth however is that this objective is accomplished just in constrained, cases and that too with trouble. Regardless, the code delivered by straight forward incorporating calculations can regularly be made more space and time proficient. This is proficient

by applying changes on the delivered code. These changes going for advancement of accumulated code are known as code enhancement and compilers that apply code enhancing changes are called improving compilers.

The advancement might be machine ward or machine free. A machine free streamlining is an arrangement of system changes that enhance the objective code without thinking about any properties of the objective machine. Machine subordinate advancements, for example, register portion and use of unique machine guideline groupings, then again, rely on upon the objective machine.

The general execution of a system can be successfully enhanced in the event that we can recognize the oftentimes executed parts of a project and afterward make these parts as effective however much as could reasonably be expected. As indicated by Pareto standard, most projects burn through ninety for each penny of their execution time in ten percent of the code. While the real rates may change, it is regularly the case that a little division of a project represents the greater part of the running time. Profiling the run-time execution of a system on delegate information precisely distinguishes the intensely voyaged areas of a project. Shockingly, a compiler does

not have the advantage of test information, so it must make best figure as to where the system problem areas seem to be.

Practically speaking, the system's inward circles are great contender for development. In a dialect that accentuates control builds like while and for proclamations, the circles might be apparent from the linguistic structure of the system; when all is said in done, a procedure called contra/–flow investigation distinguishes circles in the stream diagram of a project.

The best strategy for choosing what changes are beneficial to put into a compiler is to gather insights about the source programs and assess the advantage of a given arrangement of improvements on a delegate test of genuine source programs

CHEPTER-8

INPUT AND OUTPUT SCREENS

Login Page

Home page

Registration

Admin home

Doctor add

View enquiry

Searching

Doctor home

Patient DETAILS

Bill payment

Room details

CHAPTER-9
**Implementation of Security for the Software
developed**

SYSTEM SECURITY MEASURES

To do an adequate job on security, a systems analyst must analyze the risk, exposure, and costs and specify measures such as passwords and encryption to provide protection. The backup copies of software and recovery restart procedures must be available when needed.

SECURITY AGAINST UNAUTHORIZED ACCESS:

- (1) Use of administrator passwords: The password provides security to the administrator of Associates user so that unauthorized user can not access the facility of Associates User.
- (2) User related checks and validations: For this software, The developer uses user related checks and validations from the user.
- (3) User authorization keys: Password checking for logging of Users.

SECURITY AGAINST DATA LOSS:

- (1) Provision of efficient data backup system : In this software an efficient system is used for adequate backup facility .
- (2) Offline data storage : this system is capable for offline data Storage.
- (3) Multiple database backup : the efficient system is use for this Software to give multiple data backup.

User Level:

User are does not change Health, Transport Information. Its only View Information and it's allowed after fill own profile and then insert username and password. User is sending Matrimonial information view any other user by allow administrator.

Administrator Level:

Administrator is able to change Health, Transport Information. Administrator is allowing matrimonial information any Change. And also allow user view bride picture and groom picture information.

CHAPTER-10
CONCLUSION AND FUTURE
APPLICATION OF THE PROJECT

FURTHER SCOPE OF THE APPLICATION

1. Though most extreme endeavors have been placed into make this report genuine in all perspectives and to take all vital presentation to guarantee that the data assembled is valid, some uncomfortable components may have inched in.
2. Some of the respondents were hesitant to part with certain data on the appearance of the affectability of the data. Likewise a few truths of figures were not uncovered as the organization strategy came in the route with the expectation of complimentary disclosure of the sought information.
3. An component of inclination may have inched in from the side of the authority met. This could likewise have brought about some sort of change of the data revealed.
4. Through an attempt was make to collect data from the most ideal source in the organization, it was hard to meet the top authorities because of their bustling calendars.
5. Most of the investigation and understandings, made for this report, depend on optional information acquired. This information could have some innate slip-ups and mistakes.
6. Finally, albeit due consideration has been taken those can sort and arrangement blunders in the report itself.

The assignments determined were not very much characterized in light of the fact that nothing was said in regards to acceptances in the venture. In spite of the fact that we gave greatest push to check the product with various approval tests, a couple of them may be available in this rendition.

- Due to restricted time accessible overview couldn't be embraced for planned 20 customers and hence must be constrained to 10.
- Communication holes exist amongst workers and administration, as seniors don't impart issue to subordinates bringing about infringement of mental contract.
- Poor remunerating system(slow)
- Poor working conditions

The impediments might be numerous and the extent of the impact of these restricting components may have a heading on the report, however it not the slightest bit modifies a definitive point of the undertaking and in light of the fact that it's very USER FRIENDLY, it would be the decision of a wide range of work force.

CONCLUSIONS

This anticipate has been a compensating background in more than one way. The whole venture work has edified us in the accompanying ranges.

a) We have picked up an understanding into the working of the HOSPITAL. This speaks to an average genuine circumstance.

b) Our comprehension of database configuration has been reinforced this is on the grounds that so as to produce the last reports of database planning must be legitimately taken after.

c) Scheduling a venture and holding fast to that timetable makes a solid feeling of time administration.

d) Sense of cooperation has created and certainty of taking care of genuine venture has expanded all things considered.

e) Initially, there were issue with the acceptance however with talks, we were to execute approvals.

CHAPTER-11

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